

EFFECT OF HYPERTHYROIDISM ON THE METABOLISM OF VITAMIN C.

By S. N. RAY.

The amount of vitamin C required by guinea-pigs for complete protection is greater in the case of animals fed on desiccated thyroid. In rats, thyroid feeding has no effect on the concentration of ascorbic acid in liver or suprarenals but the concentration of the vitamin in kidney is greatly diminished. This diminution is roughly proportional to the amount of thyroid ingested by the animals.

In recent years, a number of papers have been published trying to establish a definite relationship between vitamin C requirement and the metabolic activity. Thus Harrison (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 1501) and Euler and Klusmann (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1933, 219, 215) showed that tissue slices from scorbutic animals have a low oxygen uptake and Soderstrom and Tornblom (*Skand. Arch. Physiol.*, 1933, 66, 67) have shown that the oxygen uptake of animals is lowered in scurvy. Ecklen and Kooy (*Acta Brev. Neerland Physiol.*, 1934, 3, 169) showed that when rats were fatigued by long exercise on a treadmill, the ascorbic acid in the suprarenal and in the liver fell to a low level. Abbasy, Harris, Ray and Marrack (*Lancet*, 1935, 1399) also found that the vitamin C output in the urine was much diminished during fever. These results, which indicate a proportionality between vitamin C requirements and metabolic rate, are supported by the fact that the vitamin is usually found in places where active growth is taking place.

This work was started in order to collect more information on this question. The object was essentially to establish a more quantitative relationship between vitamin C intake and the metabolism of the body taken as a whole. The results obtained fully confirmed the theory that the vitamin C requirement is proportional to the metabolic rate. Other interesting results were also obtained and the experimental findings are detailed below.

After various trials the administration of desiccated thyroid to the experimental animals was found to be the most suitable means of increasing the metabolic rate. The other recognised method, *i.e.*, forced exercise was not found suitable. Guinea-pig weighing from 250 to 300 g. were kept on a basal diet of oats, bran, dried egg-yolk and salt-mixture. To provide sufficient vitamins A and D, two drops of cod-liver oil were given to each animal per day. The animals were divided into several groups. Some of the groups were given ascorbic acid in addition to their basal diet, while others were given the basal diet supplemented with desiccated

thyroid and ascorbic acid. One group served as the negative control and was given the basal diet alone. After fourteen days all the animals were killed and cross-sections of the roots of the incisors were prepared by the usual method. The degree of protection as measured on the Key and Elphick's scale (*Biochem J.*, 1931, 26, 888) gave directly the antiscorbutic activities of the supplements in each group. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Supplement.	Degree of protection. (complete protection = 4)
100 Mg. desiccated thyroid + 1 mg. ascorbic acid	2, 0, 0, 1 (aver. 0.75)
100 Mg. desiccated thyroid + 2 mg. ascorbic acid	1, 2.5, 2.5 (aver. 2)
1 Mg. ascorbic acid only	7, 2, 2 (aver. 1.6)
2 Mg. ascorbic acid only	3, 3, 4, 4 (aver. 3.5)
Basal diet alone	0, 0.5 (aver. 0.25)

These results demonstrate that the amount of vitamin C usually necessary for protecting the animal from scorbutic symptoms becomes insufficient for the proper maintenance of animals whose metabolic rate has been increased through the administration of thyroid.

It was decided also to examine the effect of the thyroid administration to rats. These animals are known to live for indefinite periods on a strictly vitamin C-free diet and the assumption is made that these animals can synthesise their own vitamin C. As has already been mentioned, Ecklen and Kooy (*loc. cit.*) had found that forced exercise in rats reduced the ascorbic acid content of their livers and suprarenals. It was naturally thought that perhaps the same result would be obtained with thyroid feeding. But surprisingly enough it was noticed that in rats to which moderately large doses of desiccated thyroid were administered, the vitamin C content of the livers and suprarenals did not show much variation from similar tissues of rats kept on a scorbutic diet. One marked discrepancy was, however, seen in the ascorbic acid content of kidney, the concentration of the acid being much less in the kidneys of the thyroid-fed animals. On repeating the experiment, the same result was obtained and, moreover, it was observed that the diminution in the ascorbic acid content of the kidneys was roughly proportional to the amount of desiccated thyroid fed. The results are given in Table II.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In order to prevent the ingestion of any exogenous vitamin C, the experimental animals were kept on a strictly scorbutic diet. Guinea-pigs

on such a diet usually survived for three to four weeks and then died of acute scurvy. Mature albino rats were used all through the experiment. Weighed amounts of desiccated thyroid were given to the animals every morning. In order to ensure that the whole amount was eaten by the rats, the food pots were removed from the cages during the night, so that the animals used to be very hungry in the morning. The doses used were invariably lapped up clean by the animals. The food pots containing the basal diet were then returned to the cages. After five days all the animals were killed, their tissues removed and extracted with 20% trichloroacetic acid and the ascorbic acid in the extract was determined by titration against a standard solution of 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol (Birch, Harris and Ray, *Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 590).

TABLE II.

Supplement;	Amount of ascorbic acid in mg./g. of wet tissue.		
	Liver.	Suprarenals.	Kidney.
Basal diet + 100 mg. desiccated thyroid	0.24	3.8	0.12
Basal diet + 250 mg. desiccated thyroid	0.22	3.2	0.09
Basal diet + 500 mg. desiccated thyroid	0.23	3.4	0.07
Basal diet alone	0.25	3.5	0.23

DISCUSSION.

This diminution of the ascorbic acid content of the kidneys due to thyroid feeding is very interesting. A similar diminution in the concentration of the vitamin in the cerebrospinal fluid due to hyperthyroidism had been recently noted by Plant and Bulow (*Klin. Wochschr.*, 1934, 18, 1744; 1935, 15, 276, 1318; *Z. Ges. Neurol. Psychiatr.*, 1935, 182, 84, 1324). On the basis of the theory that the vitamin C requirement of an animal is proportional to its metabolic activities, the ascorbic acid content of all the tissues should have been expected to diminish in case of increased metabolism. But the preferential using up of the vitamin in the kidneys alone makes the question more complicated. One possible explanation of this phenomenon seems to be that thyroid feeding stimulates the processes of oxidation in the kidney cells, whereas such processes in liver or suprarenals are not disturbed. The peculiar fixed limit of the effect on normal oxidation—40% under thyroid control—suggests also control of specific reactions rather than an uncontrolled catalysis.